

Walking the X-Minute City: Workshop Results

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1 Introductory Brainstorming

In small groups participants collected ideas about four key questions:

- What are **key aspects** of Walkability?
- What are **data & information sources** for Walkability?
- What are **methods** for Walkability assessments?
- Who are **target groups** for Walkability assessments?

2 Notes from Presentations

2.1 CTwalk and CTstreets by Vasileios Milas

2.1.1 CTwalk

- 5/15 minutes accessible areas for age diversity/children/elderly
- accessible places
- POI information together with information on who can access it (number of elderly, number of children etc. combining population information with isochrones)
- CTWalk

2.1.2 CTstreets

- city specific walkability index through a participatory approach
- example of Amsterdam
- factors from the literature
- prioritization by urban planners (Q-methodology)
- grouping by scores and themes
- <https://miliasv.github.io/CTstreets/?city=amsterdam>
- trade-off between different aspects → just looking at aggregated index might not reveal interesting details (each neighborhood has its specific strength and weaknesses)

2.2 Netascore, ZGIS by Christian Werner & Petra Stutz

- Online survey (660 participants), strong correlation (0.82) between walkability index and participants ranking for locations
- currently focus on generic approach, not focusing on specific needs of sub-groups
- connectivity at larger scale currently not considered (aggregation at hexagons)
- routing for Austria included
 - based on perceived distance
- index calculated as a weighted average

2.3 Can CLIP See Safe Streets? by Xichen Wang, . . . Illya Ilyankou (UCL)

- safety perception based on features such as lightning, surveying cameras, shops, green, . . .
- contrastive language-image pre training (CLIP)
 - embeds images and text into a shared vector for cross model comparison
 - <https://github.com/openai/CLIP>
- comparison CLIP’s zero-shot classification of street view images (mapillary) to human perception
- compare five positive and 5 negative prompts to assess the sensitivity of CLIP
- currently only 500 images
- 13 different labels
- unbalanced data (e.g. CCTV)
- good agreement
- but subjectivity is still a bottleneck
- future work:
 - expand dataset
 - trained classifiers instead of zero-shoot CLIP (e.g. DINOv2 head)
 - nighttime imagery
 - identify visual feature most predictive of perceived safety
 - how does safety perception vary across demographic groups
- currently labeling had weaknesses only 3 labeller, simple majority voting)

2.4 HiWalk by Emily C. Wilke

- <https://climate-action.heigit.org/webapp/dashboard/plugin/hiwalk>
- co-creation process, partners
- live-demo
- limitations
- next steps
 - poi accessibility

- liveliness
- transfer to bikability
- transitability

2.4.1 Discussion

- difference to NetAscore
 - co-creation
 - not focusing on a combined score (focus on professionals not on individuals)
- what is the impact on planners? do different tools/indicators always lead to the same decisions?

3 World Cafe

Participants found themselves in four groups walking between tables with a topic each.

3.1 Walkability Factors in Different Environments

We collected factors (see Table 3.1) of walkability in different environments.

Topic	Individual Factors
Landuse	Residential vs Industrial defining different environments: urban, city center, residential area, rural
Connectivity	Connection to other transport modes First Mile — Last Mile
Access to Destinations	POIs
Road Infrastructure	accessibility features requirements of wheelchair users Easiness of the indicator Surface, smoothness give space to pedestrian (no cars, ..) no cars parking on street (or scooters) acceptance of pedestrians infrastructure e.g. benches shade width
Safety	crime temporary obstacles construction sites
Aesthetics	pleasantness attractiveness
Topography	slope
Personal	familiarity travel purpose dependent time dependent
Social and Cultural	liveliness human design architectural features

Table 1: Factors

3.2 Limitations of current approaches and methods, and ideas how to solve them

3.2.1 Key Limitations

A central theme of the discussion revolved around the lack of a unified conceptual model for walkability. Due to its complex, interdisciplinary, and subjective nature, we face the problem that more and more indices pop up, concentrating on specific aspects/target groups/geographic areas/pedestrian groups, while it gets hard to make comparisons and keep an overview.

Beyond the common issues of data availability and quality in quantitative (especially GIS-based) walkability assessments, several critical limitations were extensively discussed:

- Missing perceived walkability: A gap in many GIS-based methods is the absence of the human perspective and subjective experience. One-index-fits-all-approaches are potentially unsuitable for diverse geographic regions, demographic groups, and temporal contexts, as walkability is perceived differently across these factors.
- Lack of validation: Many existing indices suffer from a lack of validation. The idea of matching walkability scores with actual live trajectory data (i.e., where people truly walk) was proposed as a possible validation method to check if indices align with real-world pedestrian behaviour.
- Generalization of indicators: Indicators used in indices are often too generalized (e.g., "greenness"), making it difficult for users to understand their exact meaning and what they actually contain.
- Maintenance issues: A practical concern raised was the "drawer problem" – the fate of walkability indices after research projects conclude, leading to a lack of ongoing maintenance and utilization.
- Stakeholder relevance: There was an emphasis on defining "Who is it for?" to ensure the developed indices are relevant and useful for specific stakeholders and end-users.

3.2.2 Strategies and Ideas for overcoming limitations

- Improving scientific communication and outreach: A critical point was bridging the gap between scientific development and practical application. Suggestions included:
 - Building "shiny demonstrations" and breaking down indices into easily understandable formats (e.g. videos).
 - Leveraging social media for outreach.
 - Developing "what-if" scenarios for stakeholders, which showcases the usefulness of such indices.
 - Employing gamification to make the results more visible and engaging for the non-scientific community.

- Fostering closer collaboration with end-users throughout the development process.
- Integrating the human perspective: To tackle the issue of lacking subjectivity, Citizens Science was highlighted as a key approach. This could involve:
 - Developing web applications where people can report on walkable or accessible regions and highlight specific issues.
- Refining weighting mechanisms: A "bottom-up" approach and/or personalized weighting were suggested to improve the relevance and accuracy of indicator weighting.
- Comparing and benchmarking indices: Given the mass of walkability indices currently available, developing a benchmark framework was proposed as a way to maintain an overview and enable comparison. Another idea was to conduct large-scale studies to compare different indices across various geographical locations to understand their applicability and limitations.

3.3 Thinking out of the box: innovative and crazy ideas for walkability

Thinking outside the box ideas clustered into several categories of ideas:

- Missing Factors and Data that are potentially not measured or collected to a satisfactory degree yet, including:

- Complete Pedestrian Network, including high resolution
- Complete Accessible Network including data on ramps, curb cuts, stairs, plazas
- Navigability or Navigational Legibility/Complexity
- High personalisation down to potentially the individual
- How to get actionable results for purposes like planning
- A unification or standardisation of metrics within walkability
- Multiscore Aggregation
- Reducing to the minimal required set of factors to remain predictable (for specific research questions)
- Developing an interoperable standard

Eventually some lines of conflict inherent in the ideas emerged. The normative ideas from planning including ideas like “good walkability” conflict with descriptive scientific ideas and the want to have research questions that are compatible with that kind of epistemology. What do we mean with “good walkability” for whom? What are we trying to predict, what is actually our question.

The need for actionable results for planning requires a selection of audience or a minimal standard that flies in the face of extreme personalisation. If there’s only the walkability of the individual, what even is there for planners to do.

3.4 Application cases, connecting points to other methods and domains

3.4.1 Application cases

Workshop participants discussed a diverse range of application cases. They identified two main target groups: end users (such as pedestrians who want to plan a trip, tourists, or people who want to be informed about the walkability in a certain area) and planners.

Routing applications were a prominent example of applications with a focus on end users. Especially moving towards highly personalized routing which takes

into account individual preferences was attributed high potential. Related to this, purpose-specific walkability assessments focused e.g on leisure, work, or sight seeing were mentioned. An interesting example application case is the 'location finder' or 'walkability compass' that would direct people (e.g. tourists) towards highly walkable areas in their proximity. Tourist maps could also benefit from integrating walkability indicators for better guidance. Furthermore, in real estate business, customers could benefit from walkability analyses to more easily find their 'perfect' location.

In planning, purpose-specific and more individualized walkability and accessibility assessments were seen as potential benefit compared to the present state-of-the-art. Combined with network analysis these could form the basis for optimized planning outcomes in regard to higher efficiency, effectivity, and space optimization. This is an example for development of walkability-based decision support systems. Maps and tools that allow stakeholders to visualize and explore environments in cities regarding their health and safety could be very valuable. Digital maps that visualize accessibility of various points of interest such as schools, health facilities, etc. which can be explored interactively may be of high impact. Given availability of very detailed and timely data, physical barriers and constraints for people with special mobility needs could be assessed and monitored for creating a more inclusive environment.

On a more general level, tracking the evolution of walkability over time e.g. within a city could provide valuable insights and provide additional evidence for decision making. Furthermore, the possibility of utilizing micro-scale walkability to proxy healthiness on a small scale was found promising.

Regarding the long-term impact of walkability assessments, workshop participants discussed the demand for implementing means to actually measure the impact of tools and methods used. As one potential impact of walkability the group mentioned the possibility to influence social mixing across different groups.

3.4.2 Connecting to other methods and domains

Workshop participants identified several disciplines and methods which might be beneficial to enhance walkability assessments or to better understand walkability and its influencing factors. In this regard social sciences were attributed high importance as they are capable of addressing subjective aspects and perceptions of pedestrians. However, the group identified the need to conduct more representative studies in order to ensure inclusiveness. Still, they acknowledged high barriers to practically implement such studies within the existing research frameworks and funding opportunities. Furthermore, intervention studies were attributed high relevance while requiring substantial effort. Insights and expertise from the field of public health regarding e.g. human sensing, observational studies, and nudging was found to be valuable. This also applies to the domains of architecture (landscape and city architecture), spatial cognition, space syntax, and sports studies. Methods such as eye tracking applied in a real-world setting, as well as simulation and scenario modelling appeared very useful. Par-

ticipants also discussed the potential of assessing accident data in relation to walkability, while being aware of limitations such as missing baseline pedestrian count data.

3.4.3 Key take-aways from this table

The discussion led to identifying key action points as well as present barriers. An overall conclusion was that we need to gain a better understanding of walkability as a concept. Conducting a thorough state-of-the-art assessment not limited to a single domain perspective but spanning numerous adjacent domains is regarded essential. However, this task appears highly complex due to the high number of publications available on this topic as well as the use of differing domain-specific terminology in related fields. Still, condensing the state-of-the-art was regarded an important step forward. This is related to the finding that we need better integration of methods, language, and data. Furthermore, benchmarking of available methods and tools was seen as a key path to advance the use and uptake of walkability assessment. Besides benchmarking, workshop participants found thorough validation and assessment of local, target-group specific aspects to be very important.

Regarding methods, the discussion led to identifying geographic information systems (GIS) and geoinformatics methods as key enablers for facilitating the integration of methods and data across domains. Open science and open data were found to be crucial for enabling transferability and collaboration. Besides collaboration, commitment of stakeholders, provision of incentives, as well as the availability of funding were seen as crucial factors for advancing walkability. When it comes to implementing (intervention) studies, activities need better synchronization between the stakeholders involved – especially cities who plan and conduct an intervention and researchers.